

Certain Subclasses Of Meromorphic Functions With Fixed Second Coefficients Associated With Generalized Polylogarithm Functions

S. R. Swamy^{1,*} and J. Nirmala²

¹Department of Computer Science and Engineering
R. V. College of Engineering
Bangalore-560 059 Karnataka, India.
e-mail : sondekola.swamy@gmail.com.
ORCID Address: <http://orcid.org/0000-0002-8088-4103>.

²Department of Mathematics, Maharani's Science College for Women
Bangalore-560 0001, Karnataka, India.
e-mail : nirmalajodalli@gmail.com:
ORCID Address : <http://orcid.org/0000-0002-1048-5609>.

ABSTRACT. In this paper we introduce and study a subclass $\mathcal{G}_P(\alpha, \lambda, \mu, \varkappa, c)$ of meromorphic univalent functions which is associated with generalized polylogarithm functions. We obtain coefficient estimates, extreme points, growth and distortion bounds, radii of meromorphically starlikeness and meromorphically convexity for the class $\mathcal{G}_P(\alpha, \lambda, \mu, \varkappa, c)$ by fixing the second coefficient. Further, it is shown that the class $\mathcal{G}_P(\alpha, \lambda, \mu, \varkappa, c)$ is closed under convex linear combination.

2010 Mathematics Subject Classification: 30C80, 30C45.

Keywords and Phrases: Meromorphic functions, meromorphically starlike functions, meromorphically convex functions.

1. INTRODUCTION

Let Σ denote the class of functions of the form

$$f(z) = z^{-1} + \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} a_n z^n \quad (1.1)$$

which are analytic in the punctured open unit disk

$$\mathbb{U}^* := \{z : z \in \mathbb{C}, 0 < |z| < 1\} =: \mathbb{U} \setminus \{0\}.$$

Let Σ_S , $\Sigma^*(\alpha)$ and $\Sigma_K(\alpha)$, ($0 \leq \alpha < 1$) denote the subclasses of Σ that are meromorphically univalent functions, meromorphically starlike functions of order α and meromorphically convex functions of order α respectively. Analytically, $f \in \Sigma^*(\alpha)$ if and only if, f is of the form (1.1) and satisfies

$$-\Re \left(\frac{zf'(z)}{f(z)} \right) > \alpha, \quad z \in \mathbb{U},$$

similarly, $f \in \Sigma_K(\alpha)$, if and only if, f is of the form (1.1) and satisfies

$$-\Re \left(1 + \frac{zf''(z)}{f'(z)} \right) > \alpha, \quad z \in \mathbb{U},$$

and similar other classes of meromorphically univalent functions have been extensively studied by Altintas et al. [2], Aouf [3, 4], Ganigi and Uralegaddi [10], Kulkarni and Joshi [14], Mogra et al. [20], Uralegadi [28], Uralegaddi and Ganigi [29] and Uralegaddi and Somanatha [30] and others [1, 7, 8, 11, 13, 17, 18, 19, 21, 22, 24, 25, 26, 27, 32].

Let Σ_P be the class of functions of the form

$$f(z) = z^{-1} + \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} a_n z^n, \quad a_n \geq 0, \quad (1.2)$$

that are analytic and univalent in $\mathbb{U}^*$. For functions $f \in \Sigma$ given by (1.1) and $g \in \Sigma$ given by

$$g(z) = z^{-1} + \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} b_n z^n, \quad (1.3)$$

we define the Hadamard product (or convolution) of $f(z)$ and $g(z)$ by

$$(f * g)(z) := z^{-1} + \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} a_n b_n z^n =: (g * f)(z). \quad (1.4)$$

For $\varkappa \in \mathbb{N}$, the set of natural numbers with $\varkappa \geq 2$, an absolutely convergent series defined as

$$Li_{\varkappa}(z) = \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{z^n}{n^{\varkappa}}$$

is known as the polylogarithm. This class of functions was invented by Leibnitz [15]. For more works on polylogarithm and meromorphic function (see [1, 27, 32]).

We consider a linear operator

$$\Omega_{\varkappa} f(z) : \Sigma \rightarrow \Sigma$$

which is defined by the following Hadamard product (or convolution) :

$$\Omega_{\varkappa} f(z) = \phi_{\varkappa}(z) * f(z) = \frac{1}{z} + \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \frac{1}{(n+2)^{\varkappa}} a_n z^n,$$

where

$$\phi_{\varkappa}(z) = z^{-2} Li_{\varkappa}(z).$$

Next, we define the linear operator

$$\sigma_{\varkappa} : \Sigma \rightarrow \Sigma$$

as follows:

$$\sigma_{\varkappa} f(z) = \left(\Omega_{\varkappa} f(z) - \frac{1}{2^{\varkappa}} a_0 \right) = \frac{1}{z} + \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{1}{(n+2)^{\varkappa}} a_n z^n.$$

For function f in the class Σ_P , we define a linear operator $\mathcal{D}_{\mu, \varkappa}^\kappa f(z)$ as follows

$$\begin{aligned} \mathcal{D}_{\mu, \varkappa}^0 f(z) &= \sigma_\varkappa f(z) \\ \mathcal{D}_{\mu, \varkappa}^1 f(z) &= (1 - \mu)\sigma_\varkappa f(z) + \mu z(\sigma_\varkappa f(z))' = \mathcal{D}_{\mu, \varkappa} f(z) \\ \mathcal{D}_{\mu, \varkappa}^2 f(z) &= \mathcal{D}_{\mu, \varkappa}(\mathcal{D}_{\mu, \varkappa} f(z)) \\ \mathcal{D}_{\mu, \varkappa}^\kappa f(z) &= \mathcal{D}_{\mu, \varkappa}(\mathcal{D}_{\mu, \varkappa}^{\kappa-1} f(z)) \\ &= \frac{1}{z} + \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} \frac{[1 + \mu(n+1)]^\kappa}{(n+2)^\varkappa} a_n z^n, \quad \kappa \in \mathbb{N}. \end{aligned}$$

Now, in the following definition, we define a subclass $\mathcal{G}_P(\alpha, \lambda, \mu, \varkappa)$ for functions in the class Σ_P .

Definition 1.1. [27]) For $0 \leq \alpha < 1$, $0 \leq \mu$, $\lambda \leq 1$, $\kappa, \varkappa \in \mathbb{N}$ and $\varkappa \geq 2$, let $\mathcal{G}_P(\alpha, \lambda, \mu, \varkappa)$ denote a subclass of Σ consisting of functions of the form (1.1) satisfying the condition that

$$\Re \left(\frac{z(\mathcal{D}_{\mu, \varkappa}^\kappa f(z))'}{(\lambda - 1)\mathcal{D}_{\mu, \varkappa}^\kappa f(z) + \lambda z(\mathcal{D}_{\mu, \varkappa}^\kappa f(z))'} \right) > \alpha, \quad z \in \mathbb{U}^*. \quad (1.5)$$

The main object of this paper is to obtain coefficient estimates, extreme points, growth and distortion bounds, radii of meromorphically starlikeness and meromorphically convexity for the class $\mathcal{G}_P(\alpha, \lambda, \mu, \varkappa, c)$ by fixing the second coefficient. Further, it is shown that the class $\mathcal{G}_P(\alpha, \lambda, \mu, \varkappa, c)$ is closed under convex linear combination. Our first theorem gives a necessary and sufficient condition for a function $f \in \mathcal{G}_P(\alpha, \lambda, \mu, \varkappa)$.

2. COEFFICIENT INEQUALITY BY FIXING THE SECOND COEFFICIENT

Furthermore, we say that a function $f \in \mathcal{G}_P(\alpha, \lambda, \mu, \varkappa)$, whenever $f(z)$ is of the form (1.2). For the class $\mathcal{G}_P(\alpha, \lambda, \mu, \varkappa)$, we derive the following characterization property:

Theorem 2.1. Let $f \in \Sigma_P$ be given by (1.2). Then $f \in \mathcal{G}_P(\alpha, \lambda, \mu, \varkappa)$ if and only if

$$\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} [n + \alpha - \alpha\lambda(1+n)] \frac{[1 + \mu(n+1)]^\kappa}{(n+2)^\varkappa} a_n \leq (1 - \alpha). \quad (2.1)$$

Proof. If $f \in \mathcal{G}_P(\alpha, \lambda, \mu, \varkappa)$, then

$$\Re \left(\frac{z(\mathcal{D}_{\mu, \varkappa}^\kappa f(z))'}{(\lambda - 1)\mathcal{D}_{\mu, \varkappa}^\kappa f(z) + \lambda z(\mathcal{D}_{\mu, \varkappa}^\kappa f(z))'} \right) = \Re \left(\frac{-1 + \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} n \frac{[1 + \mu(n+1)]^\kappa}{(n+2)^\varkappa} a_n z^{n+1}}{-1 + \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} (\lambda - 1 + n\lambda) \frac{[1 + \mu(n+1)]^\kappa}{(n+2)^\varkappa} a_n z^{n+1}} \right).$$

By letting $z \rightarrow 1^-$, we have

$$\left(\frac{-1 + \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} n \frac{[1 + \mu(n+1)]^\kappa}{(n+2)^\varkappa} a_n}{-1 + \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} (\lambda - 1 + n\lambda) \frac{[1 + \mu(n+1)]^\kappa}{(n+2)^\varkappa} a_n} \right) > \alpha.$$

This shows that (2.1) holds.

Conversely assume that (2.1) holds. It is sufficient to show that

$$\left| \frac{\omega - 1}{\omega + 1 - 2\alpha} \right| < 1,$$

where

$$\omega = \frac{z(\mathcal{D}_{\mu, \varkappa}^{\kappa} f(z))'}{(\lambda - 1)\mathcal{D}_{\mu, \varkappa}^{\kappa} f(z) + \lambda z(\mathcal{D}_{\mu, \varkappa}^{\kappa} f(z))'}.$$

Using (2.1) that

$$\begin{aligned} & \left| \frac{z(\mathcal{D}_{\mu, \varkappa}^{\kappa} f(z))' - [(\lambda - 1)\mathcal{D}_{\mu, \varkappa}^{\kappa} f(z) + \lambda z(\mathcal{D}_{\mu, \varkappa}^{\kappa} f(z))']}{z(\mathcal{D}_{\mu, \varkappa}^{\kappa} f(z))' + (1 - 2\alpha)[(\lambda - 1)\mathcal{D}_{\mu, \varkappa}^{\kappa} f(z) + \lambda z(\mathcal{D}_{\mu, \varkappa}^{\kappa} f(z))']} \right| \\ &= \left| \frac{\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} (1 - \lambda)(n + 1) \frac{[1 + \mu(n + 1)]^{\kappa}}{(n + 2)^{\varkappa}} a_n z^{n+1}}{-2(1 - \alpha) + \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} [(1 + (1 - 2\alpha)\lambda)]n + (1 - 2\alpha)(\lambda - 1)] \frac{[1 + \mu(n + 1)]^{\kappa}}{(n + 2)^{\varkappa}} a_n z^{n+1}}{\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} (1 - \lambda)(n + 1) \frac{[1 + \mu(n + 1)]^{\kappa}}{(n + 2)^{\varkappa}} a_n} \right| \\ &\leq \frac{\sum_{n=1}^{\infty} (1 - \lambda)(n + 1) \frac{[1 + \mu(n + 1)]^{\kappa}}{(n + 2)^{\varkappa}} a_n}{2(1 - \alpha) - \sum_{n=1}^{\infty} [(1 + (1 - 2\alpha)\lambda)]n + (1 - 2\alpha)(\lambda - 1)] \frac{[1 + \mu(n + 1)]^{\kappa}}{(n + 2)^{\varkappa}} a_n} \\ &\leq 1. \end{aligned}$$

Thus we have $f \in \mathcal{G}_P(\alpha, \lambda, \mu, \varkappa)$. □

For a function defined by (1.2) and in the class $\mathcal{G}_P(\alpha, \lambda, \mu, \varkappa)$, Theorem 2.1, immediately yields

$$a_1 \leq \frac{(1 - \alpha)}{(1 + \alpha(1 - 2\lambda)) \frac{[1 + 2\mu]^{\kappa}}{3^{\varkappa}}}. \tag{2.2}$$

Hence we may take

$$a_1 = \frac{(1 - \alpha)c}{(1 + \alpha(1 - 2\lambda)) \frac{[1 + 2\mu]^{\kappa}}{3^{\varkappa}}}, \quad c(0 < c < 1). \tag{2.3}$$

Motivated by the works of Aouf and Darwish [5], Aouf and Joshi [6], Ghanim and Darus [11], Magesh et al. [17], Sivasubramanian et al. [24] and Uralegaddi [28], we now introduce the following class of functions and use the similar techniques to prove our results.

Let $\mathcal{G}_P(\alpha, \lambda, \mu, \varkappa, c)$ be the subclass of $\mathcal{G}_P(\alpha, \lambda, \mu, \varkappa)$ consisting of functions of the form

$$f(z) = \frac{1}{z} + \frac{(1 - \alpha)c}{(1 + \alpha(1 - 2\lambda)) \frac{[1 + 2\mu]^{\kappa}}{3^{\varkappa}}} z + \sum_{n=2}^{\infty} [n + \alpha - \alpha\lambda(1 + n)] \frac{[1 + \mu(n + 1)]^{\kappa}}{(n + 2)^{\varkappa}} a_n z^n, \tag{2.4}$$

where $0 < c < 1$.

In our next theorem, we now find out the coefficient inequality for the class $\mathcal{G}_P(\alpha, \lambda, \mu, \varkappa, c)$.

Theorem 2.2. Let the function $f(z)$ defined by (2.4). Then $f \in \mathcal{G}_P(\alpha, \lambda, \mu, \varkappa, c)$ if and only if,

$$\sum_{n=2}^{\infty} [n + \alpha - \alpha\lambda(1 + n)] \frac{[1 + \mu(n + 1)]^\kappa}{(n + 2)^\varkappa} a_n \leq (1 - \alpha)(1 - c). \quad (2.5)$$

The result is sharp.

Proof. By putting

$$a_1 = \frac{(1 - \alpha)c}{(1 + \alpha(1 - 2\lambda)) \frac{[1 + 2\mu]^\kappa}{3^\varkappa}}, \quad 0 < c < 1, \quad (2.6)$$

in (2.1), the result is easily derived. The result is sharp for the function

$$f(z) = \frac{1}{z} + \frac{(1 - \alpha)c}{(1 + \alpha(1 - 2\lambda)) \frac{[1 + 2\mu]^\kappa}{3^\varkappa}} z + \frac{(1 - \alpha)(1 - c)}{[n + \alpha - \alpha\lambda(1 + n)] \frac{[1 + \mu(n + 1)]^\kappa}{(n + 2)^\varkappa}} z^n, \quad n \geq 2. \quad (2.7)$$

□

Corollary 2.3. If the function f defined by (2.4) is in the class $\mathcal{G}_P(\alpha, \lambda, \mu, \varkappa, c)$, then

$$a_n \leq \frac{(1 - \alpha)(1 - c)}{[n + \alpha - \alpha\lambda(1 + n)] \frac{[1 + \mu(n + 1)]^\kappa}{(n + 2)^\varkappa}}, \quad n \geq 2. \quad (2.8)$$

The result is sharp for the function $f(z)$ given by (2.7).

Next we obtain growth and distortion properties for the class $\mathcal{G}_P(\alpha, \lambda, \mu, \varkappa, c)$.

Theorem 2.4. If the function $f(z)$ defined by (2.4) is in the class $\mathcal{G}_P(\alpha, \lambda, \mu, \varkappa, c)$ for $0 < |z| = r < 1$, then we have

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{1}{r} - \frac{(1 - \alpha)c}{(1 + \alpha(1 - 2\lambda)) \frac{[1 + 2\mu]^\kappa}{3^\varkappa}} r - \frac{(1 - \alpha)(1 - c)}{(2 + \alpha(1 - 3\lambda)) \frac{[1 + 3\mu]^\kappa}{4^\varkappa}} r^2 &\leq |f(z)| \\ &\leq \frac{1}{r} + \frac{(1 - \alpha)c}{(1 + \alpha(1 - 2\lambda)) \frac{[1 + 2\mu]^\kappa}{3^\varkappa}} r + \frac{(1 - \alpha)(1 - c)}{(2 + \alpha(1 - 3\lambda)) \frac{[1 + 3\mu]^\kappa}{4^\varkappa}} r^2. \end{aligned}$$

The result is sharp for the function $f(z)$ given by

$$f(z) = \frac{1}{z} + \frac{(1 - \alpha)c}{(1 + \alpha(1 - 2\lambda)) \frac{[1 + 2\mu]^\kappa}{3^\varkappa}} z + \frac{(1 - \alpha)(1 - c)}{(2 + \alpha(1 - 3\lambda)) \frac{[1 + 3\mu]^\kappa}{4^\varkappa}} z^2.$$

Proof. Since $f \in \mathcal{G}_P(\alpha, \lambda, \mu, \varkappa, c)$, Theorem 2.2 yields,

$$a_n \leq \frac{(1 - \alpha)(1 - c)}{[n + \alpha - \alpha\lambda(1 + n)] \frac{[1 + \mu(n + 1)]^\kappa}{(n + 2)^\varkappa}}, \quad n \geq 2. \quad (2.9)$$

Thus, for $0 < |z| = r < 1$

$$\begin{aligned} |f(z)| &\leq \frac{1}{|z|} + \frac{(1-\alpha)c}{(1+\alpha(1-2\lambda)) \frac{[1+2\mu]^\kappa}{3^\varkappa}} |z| + \sum_{n=2}^{\infty} a_n |z|^n \\ &\leq \frac{1}{r} + \frac{(1-\alpha)c}{(1+\alpha(1-2\lambda)) \frac{[1+2\mu]^\kappa}{3^\varkappa}} r + r^2 \sum_{n=2}^{\infty} a_n \\ &\leq \frac{1}{r} + \frac{(1-\alpha)c}{(1+\alpha(1-2\lambda)) \frac{[1+2\mu]^\kappa}{3^\varkappa}} r + \frac{(1-\alpha)(1-c)}{(2+\alpha(1-3\lambda)) \frac{[1+3\mu]^\kappa}{4^\varkappa}} r^2 \end{aligned}$$

and

$$\begin{aligned} |f(z)| &\geq \frac{1}{|z|} - \frac{(1-\alpha)c}{(1+\alpha(1-2\lambda)) \frac{[1+2\mu]^\kappa}{3^\varkappa}} |z| - \sum_{n=2}^{\infty} a_n |z|^n \\ &\geq \frac{1}{r} - \frac{(1-\alpha)c}{(1+\alpha(1-2\lambda)) \frac{[1+2\mu]^\kappa}{3^\varkappa}} r - r^2 \sum_{n=2}^{\infty} a_n \\ &\geq \frac{1}{r} - \frac{(1-\alpha)c}{(1+\alpha(1-2\lambda)) \frac{[1+2\mu]^\kappa}{3^\varkappa}} r - \frac{(1-\alpha)(1-c)}{(2+\alpha(1-3\lambda)) \frac{[1+3\mu]^\kappa}{4^\varkappa}} r^2. \end{aligned}$$

Thus the proof of the theorem is complete. $\square$

Theorem 2.5. *If the function $f(z)$ defined by (2.4) is in the class $\mathcal{G}_P(\alpha, \lambda, \mu, \varkappa, c)$ for $0 < |z| = r < 1$, then we have*

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{1}{r^2} - \frac{(1-\alpha)c}{[1+\alpha(1-2\lambda)] \frac{[1+2\mu]^\kappa}{3^\varkappa}} - \frac{(1-\alpha)(1-c)}{[2+\alpha(1-3\lambda)] \frac{[1+3\mu]^\kappa}{4^\varkappa}} r &\leq |f'(z)| \\ &\leq \frac{1}{r^2} + \frac{(1-\alpha)c}{[1+\alpha(1-2\lambda)] \frac{[1+2\mu]^\kappa}{3^\varkappa}} + \frac{(1-\alpha)(1-c)}{[2+\alpha(1-3\lambda)] \frac{[1+3\mu]^\kappa}{4^\varkappa}} r. \end{aligned}$$

The result is sharp for the function $f(z)$ given by

$$f(z) = \frac{1}{z} + \frac{(1-\alpha)c}{[1+\alpha(1-2\lambda)] \frac{[1+2\mu]^\kappa}{3^\varkappa}} z + \frac{(1-\alpha)(1-c)}{[2+\alpha(1-3\lambda)] \frac{[1+3\mu]^\kappa}{4^\varkappa}} z^2.$$

Proof. In view of Theorem 2.2, it follows that

$$na_n \leq \frac{2n(1-\alpha)(1-c)}{[n+\alpha-\alpha\lambda(1+n)] \frac{[1+\mu(n+1)]^\kappa}{(n+2)^\varkappa}}, \quad n \geq 2. \quad (2.10)$$

Thus, for $0 < |z| = r < 1$ and making use of (2.10), we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} |f'(z)| &\leq \left| \frac{-1}{z^2} \right| + \frac{(1-\alpha)c}{[1+\alpha(1-2\lambda)] \frac{[1+2\mu]^\kappa}{3^\varkappa}} + \sum_{n=2}^{\infty} na_n |z|^{n-1}, \quad |z| = r \\ &\leq \frac{1}{r^2} + \frac{(1-\alpha)c}{[1+\alpha(1-2\lambda)] \frac{[1+2\mu]^\kappa}{3^\varkappa}} + r \sum_{n=2}^{\infty} na_n \\ &\leq \frac{1}{r^2} + \frac{(1-\alpha)c}{[1+\alpha(1-2\lambda)] \frac{[1+2\mu]^\kappa}{3^\varkappa}} + \frac{(1-\alpha)(1-c)}{[2+\alpha(1-3\lambda)] \frac{[1+3\mu]^\kappa}{4^\varkappa}} r \end{aligned}$$

and

$$\begin{aligned} |f'(z)| &\geq \left| \frac{-1}{z^2} \right| - \frac{(1-\alpha)c}{[1+\alpha(1-2\lambda)] \frac{[1+2\mu]^\kappa}{3^\varkappa}} - \sum_{n=2}^{\infty} na_n |z|^{n-1}, \quad |z| = r \\ &\geq \frac{1}{r^2} - \frac{(1-\alpha)c}{[1+\alpha(1-2\lambda)] \frac{[1+2\mu]^\kappa}{3^\varkappa}} - r \sum_{n=2}^{\infty} na_n \\ &\geq \frac{1}{r^2} - \frac{(1-\alpha)c}{[1+\alpha(1-2\lambda)] \frac{[1+2\mu]^\kappa}{3^\varkappa}} - \frac{(1-\alpha)(1-c)}{[2+\alpha(1-3\lambda)] \frac{[1+3\mu]^\kappa}{4^\varkappa}} r. \end{aligned}$$

Hence the result follows. □

Next, we shall show that the class $\mathcal{M}_P(\alpha, \lambda, c)$ is closed under convex linear combination.

Theorem 2.6. *If*

$$f_1(z) = \frac{1}{z} + \frac{(1-\alpha)c}{[1+\alpha(1-2\lambda)] \frac{[1+2\mu]^\kappa}{3^\varkappa}} z \tag{2.11}$$

and

$$f_n(z) = \frac{1}{z} + \frac{(1-\alpha)c}{[1+\alpha(1-2\lambda)] \frac{[1+2\mu]^\kappa}{3^\varkappa}} z + \sum_{n=2}^{\infty} \frac{(1-\alpha)(1-c)}{[n+\alpha-\alpha\lambda(1+n)] \frac{[1+\mu(n+1)]^\kappa}{(n+2)^\varkappa}} z^n, \quad n \geq 2. \tag{2.12}$$

Then $f \in \mathcal{G}_P(\alpha, \lambda, \mu, \varkappa, c)$ if and only if it can be expressed in the form

$$f(z) = \sum_{n=2}^{\infty} \mu_n f_n(z) \tag{2.13}$$

where $\mu_n \geq 0$ and $\sum_{n=2}^{\infty} \mu_n \leq 1$.

Proof. From (2.11)(2.12)(2.13), we have

$$f(z) = \sum_{n=2}^{\infty} \mu_n f_n(z)$$

$$= \frac{1}{z} + \frac{(1-\alpha)c}{[1+\alpha(1-2\lambda)] \frac{[1+2\mu]^\kappa}{3^\varkappa}} z + \sum_{n=2}^{\infty} \frac{(1-\alpha)(1-c)\mu_n}{[n+\alpha-\alpha\lambda(1+n)] \frac{[1+\mu(n+1)]^\kappa}{(n+2)^\varkappa}} z^n.$$

Since

$$\sum_{n=2}^{\infty} \frac{(1-\alpha)(1-c)\mu_n}{[n+\alpha-\alpha\lambda(1+n)] \frac{[1+\mu(n+1)]^\kappa}{(n+2)^\varkappa}} \frac{[n+\alpha-\alpha\lambda(1+n)] \frac{[1+\mu(n+1)]^\kappa}{(n+2)^\varkappa}}{(1-\alpha)(1-c)}$$

$$= \sum_{n=2}^{\infty} \mu_n = 1 - \mu_1 \leq 1$$

it follows from Theorem 2.1 that the function $f \in \mathcal{G}_P(\alpha, \lambda, \mu, \varkappa, c)$. Conversely, suppose that $f \in \mathcal{G}_P(\alpha, \lambda, \mu, \varkappa, c)$. Since

$$a_n \leq \frac{(1-\alpha)(1-c)}{[n+\alpha-\alpha\lambda(1+n)] \frac{[1+\mu(n+1)]^\kappa}{(n+2)^\varkappa}}, \quad n \geq 2.$$

Setting

$$\mu_n = \frac{[n+\alpha-\alpha\lambda(1+n)] \frac{[1+\mu(n+1)]^\kappa}{(n+2)^\varkappa}}{(1-\alpha)(1-c)} a_n$$

and

$$\mu_1 = 1 - \sum_{n=2}^{\infty} \mu_n.$$

It follows that

$$f(z) = \sum_{n=2}^{\infty} \mu_n f_n(z).$$

Hence the proof complete. □

Theorem 2.7. *The class $\mathcal{G}_P(\alpha, \lambda, \mu, \varkappa, c)$ is closed under linear combination.*

Proof. Suppose that the function f be given by (2.4), and let the function g be given by

$$g(z) = \frac{1}{z} + \frac{(1-\alpha)c}{[1+\alpha(1-2\lambda)] \frac{[1+2\mu]^\kappa}{3^\varkappa}} z + \sum_{n=2}^{\infty} |b_n| z^n, \quad n \geq 2.$$

Assuming that f and g are in the class $\mathcal{G}_P(\alpha, \lambda, \mu, \varkappa, c)$, it is enough to prove that the function H defined by

$$h(z) = \zeta f(z) + (1-\zeta)g(z), \quad 0 \leq \zeta \leq 1$$

is also in the class $\mathcal{G}_P(\alpha, \lambda, \mu, \varkappa, c)$. Since

$$h(z) = \frac{1}{z} + \frac{(1-\alpha)c}{[1+\alpha(1-2\lambda)] \frac{[1+2\mu]^\kappa}{3^\varkappa}} z + \sum_{n=2}^{\infty} |a_n \zeta + (1-\zeta)b_n| z^n,$$

we observe that

$$\sum_{n=2}^{\infty} [n + \alpha - \alpha\lambda(1+n)] \frac{[1 + \mu(n+1)]^\kappa}{(n+2)^\varkappa} |a_n \zeta + (1-\zeta)b_n| \leq (1-\alpha)(1-c),$$

with the aid of Theorem 2.2. Thus $h \in \mathcal{G}_P(\alpha, \lambda, \mu, \varkappa, c)$. □

Next we determine the radii of meromorphically starlikeness of order δ and meromorphically convexity of order δ for functions in the class $\mathcal{G}_P(\alpha, \lambda, \mu, \varkappa, c)$.

Theorem 2.8. *Let the function $f(z)$ defined by (2.4) be in the class $\mathcal{G}_P(\alpha, \lambda, \mu, \varkappa, c)$, then we have*

- (i) *f is meromorphically starlike of order δ ($0 \leq \delta < 1$) in the disk $|z| < r_1(\alpha, \lambda, c, \delta)$ where $r_1(\alpha, \lambda, c, \delta)$ is the largest value for which*

$$\frac{(3-\delta)(1-\alpha)c}{[1+\alpha(1-2\lambda)] \frac{[1+2\mu]^\kappa}{3^\varkappa}} r^2 + \frac{(n+2-\delta)(1-\alpha)(1-c)}{[n+\alpha-\alpha\lambda(1+n)] \frac{[1+\mu(n+1)]^\kappa}{(n+2)^\varkappa}} r^{n+1} \leq (1-\delta), \quad n \geq 2.$$

- (ii) *f is meromorphically convex of order δ ($0 \leq \delta < 1$) in the disk $|z| < r_2(\alpha, \lambda, c, \delta)$ where $r_2(\alpha, \lambda, c, \delta)$ is the largest value for which*

$$\frac{(3-\delta)(1-\alpha)c}{[1+\alpha(1-2\lambda)] \frac{[1+2\mu]^\kappa}{3^\varkappa}} r^2 + \frac{n(n+2-\delta)(1-\alpha)(1-c)}{[n+\alpha-\alpha\lambda(1+n)] \frac{[1+\mu(n+1)]^\kappa}{(n+2)^\varkappa}} r^{n+1} \leq (1-\delta), \quad n \geq 2.$$

Each of these results is sharp for the function $f_n(z)$ given by (2.7).

Proof. It is enough to highlight that

$$\left| \frac{zf'(z)}{f(z)} + 1 \right| \leq 1 - \delta, \quad |z| < r_1.$$

Thus, we have

$$\left| \frac{zf'(z)}{f(z)} + 1 \right| = \left| \frac{\frac{-1}{z} + \frac{(1-\alpha)c}{[1+\alpha(1-2\lambda)] \frac{[1+2\mu]^\kappa}{3^\varkappa}} z + \sum_{n=2}^{\infty} na_n z^n + \frac{1}{z} + \frac{(1-\alpha)c}{[1+\alpha(1-2\lambda)] \frac{[1+2\mu]^\kappa}{3^\varkappa}} z + \sum_{n=2}^{\infty} a_n z^n}{\frac{1}{z} + \frac{(1-\alpha)c}{[1+\alpha(1-2\lambda)] \frac{[1+2\mu]^\kappa}{3^\varkappa}} z + \sum_{n=2}^{\infty} a_n z^n} \right|. \tag{2.14}$$

Hence (2.14) holds true if

$$\frac{(1-\alpha)c}{[1+\alpha(1-2\lambda)]\frac{[1+2\mu]^\kappa}{3^\varkappa}}r^2 + \sum_{n=2}^{\infty}(n+1)a_n r^{n+1} \leq (1-\delta) \left[1 - \frac{(1-\alpha)c}{[1+\alpha(1-2\lambda)]\frac{[1+2\mu]^\kappa}{3^\varkappa}}r^2 - \sum_{n=2}^{\infty} a_n r^{n+1} \right], \quad (2.15)$$

or,

$$\frac{(3-\delta)(1-\alpha)c}{[1+\alpha(1-2\lambda)]\frac{[1+2\mu]^\kappa}{3^\varkappa}}r^2 + \sum_{n=2}^{\infty}(n+2-\delta)a_n r^{n+1} \leq (1-\delta) \quad (2.16)$$

and it follows that from (2.5), we may take

$$a_n \leq \frac{(1-\alpha)(1-c)}{[n+\alpha-\alpha\lambda(1+n)]\frac{[1+\mu(n+1)]^\kappa}{(n+2)^\varkappa}}\mu_n, \quad n \geq 2, \quad (2.17)$$

where $\mu_n \geq 0$ and $\sum_{n=2}^{\infty} \mu_n \leq 1$.

For each fixed r , we choose the positive integer $n_0 = n_0(r_0)$ for which

$$\frac{(n+2-\delta)}{[n+\alpha-\alpha\lambda(1+n)]\frac{[1+\mu(n+1)]^\kappa}{(n+2)^\varkappa}}r^{n+1},$$

is maximal. Then it follows that

$$\sum_{n=2}^{\infty}(n+2-\delta)a_n r^{n+1} \leq \frac{(n_0+2-\delta)(1-\alpha)(1-c)}{[n_0+\alpha-\alpha\lambda(1+n_0)]\frac{[1+\mu(n_0+1)]^\kappa}{(n_0+2)^\varkappa}}r^{n_0+1}. \quad (2.18)$$

Then f is starlike of order δ in $0 < |z| < r_1(\alpha, \lambda, c, \delta)$ provided that

$$\frac{(3-\delta)(1-\alpha)c}{[1+\alpha(1-2\lambda)]\frac{[1+2\mu]^\kappa}{3^\varkappa}}r^2 + \frac{(n_0+2-\delta)(1-\alpha)(1-c)}{[n_0+\alpha-\alpha\lambda(1+n_0)]\frac{[1+\mu(n_0+1)]^\kappa}{(n_0+2)^\varkappa}}r^{n_0+1} \leq (1-\delta). \quad (2.19)$$

We find the value $r_0 = r_0(k, c, \delta, n)$ and the corresponding integer $n_0(r_0)$ so that

$$\frac{(3-\delta)(1-\alpha)c}{[1+\alpha(1-2\lambda)]\frac{[1+2\mu]^\kappa}{3^\varkappa}}r_0^2 + \frac{(n_0+2-\delta)(1-\alpha)(1-c)}{[n_0+\alpha-\alpha\lambda(1+n_0)]\frac{[1+\mu(n_0+1)]^\kappa}{(n_0+2)^\varkappa}}r_0^{n_0+1} = (1-\delta). \quad (2.20)$$

It is the value for which the function $f(z)$ is starlike in $0 < |z| < r_0$.

(ii) In a similar manner, we can prove our result providing the radius of meromorphically convexity of order δ ($0 \leq \delta < 1$) for functions in the class $\mathcal{G}_P(\alpha, \lambda, \mu, \varkappa, c)$, so we skip the proof of (ii). $\square$

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